

MAPPING THE FIELD OF MULTILEVEL AMBIDEXTERITY RESEARCH WITHIN ORGANIZATIONS USING BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Multilevel ambidexterity is an emerging but not yet fully explored theme in paradox research. Although organizational ambidexterity represents a well-established and mature level of analysis, research on unit/team and job/individual ambidexterity remains in its early stages of development. A bibliometric analysis has been conducted to provide an updated and integrative literature review of the current structure, trends, and research gaps in the ambidexterity literature. The goal was to assess the past (performance analysis), examine the present (co-authorship, co-[key]words or co-occurrence, and co-citation analyses), and anticipate future directions (bibliographic coupling) of interorganizational, organizational, unit (team), and individual (employee/job) ambidexterity. The search utilized the Web of Science Core Collection database, yielding 900 primary and 24,742 secondary prefiltered publications covering the period up to September 2024. The findings from science mapping guide scholars toward future theoretical and strategic frameworks that help organizational practitioners address the balancing challenges encountered at multiple levels of analysis.

Keywords: Multilevel Ambidexterity, Organizational Ambidexterity, Unit Ambidexterity, Individual Ambidexterity, Bibliometric Analysis

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1 INTRODUCTION

Within the last two decades, multilevel ambidexterity has become a significant yet implicit stream of paradox research that offers valuable insights for organizations seeking to balance ambidextrous polarities. Ambidexterity per se represents how organizations balance exploring new opportunities with exploiting existing core capabilities (Jansen et al., 2016). The balance between revolutionary and incremental change influences short-term performance (March, 1991), competitive advantage, and longevity (Chakma et al., 2024). As

a complex, paradoxical concept involving information processing (Rosari et al., 2024), ambidexterity is still evolving, continuously expanding our understanding and involving novel business challenges.

From a practical standpoint, multilevel ambidexterity is a fundamental organizational challenge; managers continuously strive to develop specific ambidextrous capabilities, skills, and abilities to engage the workforce in sufficient exploitation (to secure present viability) while simultaneously dedicating enough effort to exploration (to ensure sustainability). Raisch and Birkinshaw (2008) were among the first to emphasize that the level of analysis plays a

critical role in the development of ambidexterity studies. Recent ambidexterity studies indicate that this innovation–efficiency tension should be realized across various domains (organizational units) and among individual employees (Snehvrat et al., 2017). However, the theoretical understanding and business knowledge are limited and inadequate regarding how ambidexterity can be applied in various domains (Chakma et al., 2024) and managed in practice within multilevel organizational structures (Turner et al., 2013). The origins and outcomes of ambidexterity have predominantly been studied at a single (i.e., organizational) level of analysis, but researchers increasingly recognize the need to evaluate its multilevel effects (Cantarello et al., 2012; Katou, 2021; Kontopoulos et al., 2021).

More comprehensively, ambidexterity has been examined internally and externally at micro and macro levels. Raisch and Birkinshaw (2008) notably discussed the distinction between internal and external ambidexterity. While internal (organizational) ambidexterity refers to an organization's ability to manage both exploration and exploitation within its boundaries (Birkinshaw & Gibson, 2004; He & Wong, 2004; Jansen et al., 2012), external (interorganizational) ambidexterity ties directly to organizational ambidexterity and entails distributing ambidextrous behaviors through partnerships, alliances, or collaborations with external entities (Lavie et al., 2010; O'Reilly & Tushman, 2004). On the other hand, Kontopoulos et al. (2021) distinguished between micro-level scholars, who focus on individual/employee/job ambidexterity, and macro-level scholars, who concentrate on interorganizational, organizational, and team/unit ambidexterity.

Moving downwards, team ambidexterity represents a collective capability between the organizational and individual levels. It represents an effort to balance organizational exploration (innovative) and exploitation (operational) strategies as well as the dynamics among team members (Gibson & Birkinshaw, 2004). Whereas team ambidexterity emphasizes the collective behavioral dynamics of a small working group that balances exploration and exploitation, the closely related yet broader term unit ambidexterity generally refers to the strategic ability of a specific (formal) organizational unit, such as a department or division (Jansen et al., 2018; Kostopoulos et al., 2015).

The lowest level of analysis is represented by individual ambidexterity, which highlights a person's ability to alternate between innovative (exploratory) and operational (exploitative) thinking through cognitive and behavioral capabilities (Mom et al., 2015, 2019; Raisch & Birkinshaw, 2008). Often used interchangeably, the term employee ambidexterity is narrower in focus, concentrating on how employees within an organization balance their job roles to contribute to both innovation and efficiency (Caniëls et al., 2017; Caniëls & Veld, 2019; Mom et al., 2009).

These interconnected concepts collectively impact an organization's ability to balance exploration (innovation) and exploitation (efficiency). However, the understanding of how they can operate across levels of analysis remains insufficient. Interorganizational ambidexterity links establish a synergistic foundation for a top-down and bottom-up cascading multilevel effect in which each level influences the other. The interplay among various levels—organizational, team, and individual—can significantly improve an organization's goal of balancing all-level polarities for integrative ambidexterity.

The substantial volume of published ambidexterity research and its continuous growth demands that scholars contextualize each case effectively (Romanelli et al., 2021) by reflecting the interdisciplinarity of the field and the interconnectedness of its structures. This is why rigor and diverse quantitative bibliometric analysis for citation databases should be conducted regularly (Zupic & Cater, 2015) to determine the trajectory of scientific progress, ultimately aiding practitioners in achieving multilevel alignment. Multilevel ambidexterity research has reached unprecedented maturity in scope and size, making it more suitable than ever for a bibliometric review.

In an insightful paper, Turner et al. (2013) presented a systematic review aimed at developing a research framework that integrates intellectual capital resources—organizational, social, and human capital—across multiple levels of analysis. Additionally, a notable single-level qualitative study and bibliometric review by Popadić and Milohnić (2016) illustrated two decades of organizational ambidexterity's structural development. Likewise, several prolific scholars have made initial efforts to review the existing knowledge base on organizational am-

bidexterity using the Scopus database (Amjad & Nor, 2020; Chakma et al., 2024; Kononiuk, 2022) or Web of Science Core Collection (WoSCC) database (Garcia-Lillo et al., 2017). However, only Zahoor et al. (2021) interconnected the field of organizational ambidexterity in the context of interorganizational alliances by merging evidence from both databases. Previous studies have been carried out applying various research designs, types of ambidexterity, and industries, giving mixed and unconnected findings that are influenced by the researchers' specific choices (Popadić & Milohnić, 2016).

The papers above provided informative insights with interesting preliminary findings that yielded specific theoretical and practical contributions; however, they were primarily concentrated on past and present research rather than future directions. Furthermore, no author has yet conducted a comprehensive bibliometric analysis on multilevel ambidexterity, despite Rosari et al. (2024) suggesting that research should approach the ambidexterity phenomenon across various levels. Therefore, the purpose of the present study was to assess the past (performance analysis), examine the present (co-authorship, co-word, and co-citation analyses), and anticipate future directions (bibliographic coupling) of ambidexterity in the multilevel context. The search utilized the WoSCC database, yielding 900 primary (identified from our keyword search) and 24,742 secondary publications (i.e., cited by the primary ones). In particular, the paper was intended to address four research questions: (RQ1) Which authors have had the most significant influence on multilevel ambidexterity research regarding networking, productivity, and citations? (RQ2) What are the primary topics associated with multilevel ambidexterity research? (RQ3) What does the intellectual structure of the multilevel ambidexterity literature look like? (RQ4) What relevant emerging and future directions exist for multilevel ambidexterity research?

This bibliometric analysis maps an updated and integrative quantitative literature overview on ambidexterity in the multilevel context. It provides essential insights for scholars interested in multilevel ambidexterity to conceptualize more deeply. It guides managers and professionals in navigating various polarities across various organizational levels that demand their awareness and updated

strategic frameworks. The paper also discusses future research directions, highlighting the necessity for robust theory development supported by methodological improvements and a qualitative approach.

2 METHOD

Using citation databases as their primary source, bibliometric studies can handle large datasets efficiently, making them more effective than manual approaches to quantitative and qualitative data analysis (Ramos-Rodríguez & Ruíz-Navarro, 2004). The analysis in this paper employed the WoSCC as the most commonly used database for bibliometric reviews (Zupic & Cater, 2015); it serves as a platform that encompasses a wide range of significant scientific findings across the social sciences. Given that bibliometric methodologies utilize extensive inclusion criteria that encompass time, methods, and references (Vogel et al., 2021), the initial search, conducted in late September 2024, included the selected six keywords ("*interorganizational ambidexterity*" OR "*organizational ambidexterity*" OR "*team ambidexterity*" OR "*unit ambidexterity*" OR "*individual ambidexterity*" OR "*employee ambidexterity*") and returned 1,633 publications meeting the elementary research field size requirement for bibliometric review tools of 500+ papers (Donthu et al., 2021).

The keyword "*ambidexterity*" was chosen instead of the suggested abbreviations "*ambidex**" or "*ambidext**" (Örtenblad, 2010) to provide a more focused term. Additionally, the keywords "*job ambidexterity*", "*multilevel ambidexterity*", and "*multilevel ambidexterity*" did not make any difference in results, so they were omitted. To implement a comprehensive methodological approach, the paper analyzes a more extensive sample than previous bibliometric reviews of single-level ambidexterity. By identifying relevant WoSCC sources of articles, selecting search terms along with their synonyms, building a search strategy that establishes a 20-year viable timespan (from 2004 until 2024) focused on *topics* to highlight the latest trends that have emerged since the last research, and developing science mapping after in the analysis, the paper improved the overall quality of bibliometric studies as recommended by Romanelli et al. (2021).

To conclude the process with 900 publications, a gradual refinement approach was implemented through a series of six inclusion criteria: *Document Type*, *WoS Categories*, *Language*, *WoS Index*, *Citation Topics Meso*, and *Citation Topics Micro*. The selected publications, mainly journal articles, were in English and focused on management and business studies. Additionally, the analysis incorporated the SSCI (Social Sciences Citation Index), which serves as a vital source of information for conducting bibliometric analyses in the field of social sciences. The gathered bibliometric data were meticulously examined for unrelated papers and erroneous entries to ensure reliable insights. As the final step before analyzing via VOSviewer software, the complete extracted records and their cited references were imported. To ensure the repeatability of the search, the complete search strategy, including the search terms and criteria, is detailed in *Figure 1*.

The bibliometric analysis included performance assessment and science mapping (Lim & Kumar, 2024), utilizing the 3Ss concept of sense-

making—scanning, sensing, and substantiating to navigate the complexity and uncover actionable and meaningful insights. The performance analysis serves as an evaluative method for assessing research constituents’ productivity (Romanelli et al., 2021) and impact/contribution (Lim & Kumar, 2024) by using a variety of metrics. Conversely, science mapping, often called bibliometric networks, involves clustering knowledge around key themes, trends, and gaps in scientific literature. This method analyzes intellectual interactions and structural connections among authors, institutions, and keywords (Donthu et al., 2021; Romanelli et al., 2021). By introducing this quantitative tool for considerable data extraction, the paper provides a “big-picture” view of the field’s performance and the interconnectedness (or lack thereof) in its intellectual structure (Donthu et al., 2021; Romanelli et al., 2021). This approach helps interpret theoretical and practical implications (Lim & Kumar, 2024) and bridges the gap between quantitative data and qualitative interpretation.

Figure 1: Search strategy and methodological procedure

3 RESULTS

3.1 Performance analysis

Performance analysis is one of the standard components of bibliometric analysis, and it quantifies the impact and productivity of authors, journals, institutions, or countries. It answers “who, when, where, and what” questions (Romanelli et al., 2021) by assessing publication (i.e., trends, output) and citation (i.e., counts) metrics (Lim & Kumar, 2024). It represents an attempt to objectively identify patterns and understand the root causes to set the stage for descriptive, in-depth interpretation (Lim & Kumar, 2024). The present paper is focused on publication- and author-based performance metrics with paper reviews based on the WoSCC search strategy results.

3.1.1 Publication-based descriptives

The WoSCC search resulted in 900 publications on multilevel ambidexterity spanning 859 scientific journals. Gibson and Birkinshaw (2004) wrote a pioneering paper with multilevel insights explaining contextual organizational ambidexterity, defined as the capacity to achieve alignment and adaptability at a business-unit level simultaneously. Over the years, scholars have progressively introduced new levels of ambidexterity, expanding the concept beyond its initial focus. For example, unit ambidexterity was introduced by O’Connor and DeMartino (2006), followed by team ambidexterity (Haas, 2010), individual ambidexterity (Torres et al., 2015),

employee ambidexterity (Caniels et al., 2017), and most recently, interorganizational ambidexterity (Lo & Theodoraki, 2021).

As a result, after two decades of ambidexterity research, a growing body of work now discusses this phenomenon through a multilevel lens, although the mainstream publications have primarily examined organizational ambidexterity. Nevertheless, in the last two decades (see *Figure 2*), research on multilevel ambidexterity has experienced significant growth in both publications and citations. Starting in 2020, this trend appears to follow an inverted U-shaped curve. The publication trend has mirrored that of citations, with the highest number of publications recorded in 2020 (n=130) and the peak in citations occurring in 2022 (n=8,390). Since then, both metrics have shown a declining trend. An introductory phase characterized the initial decade of publications; however, since 2015, more than 50 papers have been published yearly. Just a year prior, this trend was observed in citations for the first time, surpassing a thousand citations annually. Although the annual citation growth rate from 2004 to 2024 was 82.34%, marked by numerous fluctuations, the growth rate has slowed to just 7% in the last five years, indicating a downward trend caused by saturation. The publication score for 2024 (n=40) is still awaiting updates from WoSCC at the end of the year, including data from the last three months, and given that the number of citations—particularly for older, highly cited works—tends to increase over time, expectations suggest that this upward trend is likely to persist.

Figure 2: Publications and citations on multilevel ambidexterity across years (2004–2024)

The journal quality analysis revealed that 40% of multilevel ambidexterity papers (n=364) were published in prominent scholarly management and business journals indexed in WoSCC. Among the 16 journals with more than 15 published documents, only one is not classified in the Q1 quartile (see *Table 1*). The *Journal of Business Research* (46 documents) has established itself as the leading academic outlet for multilevel ambidexterity research, focusing on knowledge management concerning innovation, new business models, R&D, and entrepreneurship. This research often explores the balance between exploration and exploitation in interorganizational and organizational contexts. *Management Decision* (31 documents) is another prominent outlet emphasizing the organizational ambidexterity–performance relationship. It published studies such as those on enhancing organizational adaptability and innovation through strategic flexibility, knowledge management, and job satisfaction, particularly at team and individual (employee) ambidexterity levels. The relationship between human resource management (HRM) prac-

tices and behavior with organizational, team, and employee ambidexterity emerged as the dominant theme in the *International Journal of Human Resource Management* (27 documents).

Table 2 presents the top 10 most cited publications on multilevel ambidexterity. Gibson and Birkinshaw's (2004) paper, "The Antecedents, Consequences, and Mediating Role of Organizational Ambidexterity," stands out as the oldest and the most cited publication with 2,493 total citations. The paper is regarded as one of the most significant contributions to ambidexterity research theory. Its impact has shaped much of the foundational understanding of how organizations balance alignment and adaptability and how it affects the unit level. Smith and Lewis (2011) lead in citations per year, averaging 148.71, for their highly cited paper, "Toward a Theory of Paradox: A Dynamic Equilibrium Model of Organizing," which has amassed a total of 2,082 citations. The authors explored the paradoxical tensions present in organizational environments. They proposed a dynamic equilibrium model demonstrating how cyclical responses to these tensions foster sustainable performance and future success.

Table 1: Publication sources with 15 or more documents published

<i>Journal</i>	<i>WoSCC category quartile</i>	<i>Number of documents published</i>
<i>Journal of Business Research</i>	Q1	46
<i>Management Decision</i>	Q1	31
<i>International Journal of Human Resource Management</i>	Q1	27
<i>Long Range Planning</i>	Q1	27
<i>International Business Review</i>	Q1	25
<i>Technological Forecasting and Social Change</i>	Q1	25
<i>IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management</i>	Q1	24
<i>Industrial Marketing Management</i>	Q1	24
<i>Journal of Management Studies</i>	Q1	21
<i>Journal of Business Industrial Marketing</i>	Q1	18
<i>Business Process Management Journal</i>	Q1	17
<i>Journal of Knowledge Management</i>	Q1	17
<i>Human Resource Management</i>	Q1	16
<i>Journal of Product Innovation Management</i>	Q1	16
<i>Organization Science</i>	Q1	15
<i>Technology Analysis Strategic Management</i>	Q2	15

Recognizing that older publications authored by prominent researchers typically achieve higher annual citation scores, it is evident that their influence in the field remains significant over time. Similarly, a few recently published papers have already garnered high citation scores. For example, Del Giudice et al. (2021) investigated how digital innovation is influenced by the three pillars of self-tuning models—agility, adaptation, and ambidexterity. Bucci et al. (2020) examined how new international ventures shape ambidextrous innovation and dynamic marketing capabilities necessary to support international performance. Mahmood and Mubarak (2020) positioned their study between innovation and polarities of organizational ambidexterity in the context of the fourth industrial revolution. Despite being published in various journals, the common thread among these promising papers is their focus on innovation ambidexterity.

3.1.2 Author-based descriptives

The analysis identified 2,078 scholars across 69 countries, with the United States (n=211), the United Kingdom (n=204), and China (n=160) being the most represented. Forty-six authors have published five or more papers. Among all authors, the first 11 most cited scholars emerged as leaders in the field, accounting for nearly 11.22% of all publications. In comparison, five scholars were recognized as the most productive, each having published at least seven papers (see Table 3). Julian Birkinshaw (6,464 citations) is the most cited author, followed by Marianne Lewis (4,466 citations). Birkinshaw’s co-authors, Sebastian Raisch (4,342 citations) and Michael L. Tushman (3,510 citations), rank prominently on the citation list, alongside Lewis’s co-author, Wendy K. Smith (4,025 citations). All five authors have established themselves in ambidexterity and organizational paradoxes,

Table 2: Top 10 cited publications

Author(s)	Topic	Source Title	Total citations	Citations per year
Gibson & Birkinshaw (2004)	The antecedents, consequences, and mediating role of organizational ambidexterity	<i>Academy of Management Journal</i>	2,493	118.71
Smith & Lewis (2011)	Toward a theory of paradox: A dynamic equilibrium model of organizing.	<i>Academy of Management Review</i>	2,082	148.71
Raisch & Birkinshaw (2008)	Organizational ambidexterity: Antecedents, outcomes, and moderators	<i>Journal of Management</i>	1,487	87.47
Raisch et al. (2009)	Organizational ambidexterity: Balancing exploitation and exploration for sustained performance	<i>Organization Science</i>	1,280	80
Andriopoulos & Lewis (2009)	Exploitation–exploration tensions and organizational ambidexterity: Managing paradoxes and innovation	<i>Organization Science</i>	1,268	79.25
O’Reilly & Tushman (2013)	Organizational ambidexterity: Past, present, and future	<i>Academy of Management Perspectives</i>	1,239	103.25
Cao et al. (2009)	Unpacking organizational ambidexterity: Dimensions, contingencies, and synergistic effects	<i>Organization Science</i>	927	57.94
Schad et al. (2016)	Paradox research in management science: Looking back to move forwards	<i>Academy of Management Annals</i>	685	76.11
Jansen et al. (2009)	Structural differentiation and ambidexterity: The mediating role of integration mechanisms	<i>Organization Science</i>	658	41.13
Simsek (2009)	Organizational ambidexterity: Towards a multilevel understanding	<i>Journal of Management Studies</i>	598	37.38

maintaining similar rankings regarding publication output and productivity. To offer a more balanced assessment of scholarly contributions, we evaluated productivity based on the number of active years in publication. This analysis revealed that Wendy K. Smith and Shlomo Y. Tarba have the highest annual productivity, with an average of 1.75 publications per active year, followed by Sebastian Raisch and Neil Turner, who average 1.50 publications per active year. Despite having joined the field in this decade with fewer than 1,000 citations, Turner and his co-authors (2013) have made significant theoretical and practical contributions to multilevel ambidexterity through their review paper entitled “Mechanisms for Managing Ambidexterity: A Review and Research Agenda.”

In terms of co-authorship patterns, the majority of publications were produced by a three-author team (37.44%), followed by two- (23.11%) and four-author (22.56%) teams. Only 7.22% of publications are solo-authored. The leading institutions affiliated

with multilevel ambidexterity research include Erasmus University Rotterdam from the Netherlands (48 documents) and four universities from the United Kingdom: University of London (28 documents), University of Birmingham (23 documents), University of Warwick (23 documents), and Cranfield University (15 documents). Additionally, the University of St. Gallen from Switzerland has contributed 20 documents, while the Chinese Academy of Sciences has published 15 documents. Collectively, these seven institutions represent 19.11% of total publications, indicating that multilevel ambidexterity has yet to gain broader acceptance across academic institutions.

3.1.3 Number of publications identified through the search strategy

The added value of the quantitative bibliometric analysis is illustrated through a simple graphic depicting multilevel ambidexterity (see *Figure 3*).

Table 3: Most cited and most productive authors

Author	Affiliation	Citations	Publications	Annual Productivity ¹
Birkinshaw, Julian	University of London (UK)	6,464	9	1.12
Lewis, Marianne W.	University of Cincinnati (USA)	4,466	6	1.20
Raisch, Sebastian	University of Geneva (SWI)	4,342	12	1.50
Smith, Wendy K.	University of Delaware (USA)	4,025	7	1.75
Tushman, Michael L.	Harvard University (USA)	3,510	7	1.16
Jansen, Justin J. P.	Erasmus University (NED)	1,971	16	1.23
Simsek, Zeki	University of South Carolina (USA)	1,508	7	1.16
Volberda, Henk W.	University of Amsterdam (NED)	1,371	8	1.00
Tarba, Shlomo Y.	University of Birmingham (UK)	1,361	14	1.75
Turner, Neil	Cranfield University (UK)	748	9	1.50
Junni, Paulina	Aalto University (FIN)	740	6	1.20

¹ Publications per active year

Figure 3: Levels of analysis in multilevel ambidexterity research

It is categorized into external (interorganizational) and internal ambidexterity. Internal ambidexterity is further divided into three levels: organizational, team (unit), and individual (employee) ambidexterity. This graphic displays the number of publications resulting from the keyword selection and search strategy and the number of papers exploring the interrelations between levels (see Figure 3). This figure assists scholars in identifying potential literature gaps and provides insights into the frequency of keyword usage.

3.2 Science mapping

Science mapping (bibliometric networks; bibliometric mapping) seeks to uncover scientific fields' knowledge structure and dynamics (Zupic & Cater, 2015). It visualizes structure in scientific literature by analyzing connections among authors and institutions, publications, citations, and keywords (Romanelli et al., 2021). It is used to evaluate the social and intellectual foundations of a discipline, aiming

to answer key questions such as "what," "why," and "how" to understand comprehensive relationships. It helps to uncover the core theories, concepts, contexts, topics, methods, or motivations that shape the research landscape. Various mapping methods are frequently employed, utilized in this paper to analyze the current state of research by conducting co-authorship, co-(key)words or co-occurrence, and co-citation analyses. Furthermore, bibliographic coupling will be applied to forecast potential future research directions.

3.2.1 Co-authorship analysis

Co-authorship analysis examines how scholars interact, engage, and form informal social networks that lead to formal collaborations. It assesses these collaborations among authors, institutions, and countries by analyzing the number of joint publications they have produced together (Hicks, 2004; Zupic & Cater, 2015). Network metrics offer insights

into trends in interinstitutional partnerships, research practices, and synergies over time (Reyes-Gonzales et al., 2016). They highlight authors' relative significance, geographic distribution, gender representation, and the dynamics within research teams. Works by multiple authors generally receive more citations than solo-authored papers, reflecting a broader influence (Katz & Hicks, 1997), but "knowledge brokers"—those who bridge various research groups—may not consistently be recognized through their publication or citation counts (Donthu et al., 2021).

Out of the 2,123 authors recognized in VOSviewer, this work is concentrated on researchers who met the criterion of having published at least five papers. Five "invisible colleagues" clusters were identified (see Figure 4). The largest cluster (red, N=6) consists of scholars recognized as pioneers in paradox and ambidexterity research (Birkinshaw, Lewis, Smith, Tushman, Zimmermann, and Raisch), who are the key brokers between these and other clusters. The second largest cluster (green, N=4) primarily comprises scholars from the United Kingdom (Tarba), Finland (Junni), Pakistan (Khan), and Taiwan (Chang). Their research is predominantly focused on HRM practices within organizational ambidexterity, mergers and acquisitions and small and medium-

sized enterprises. The third largest (blue, N=4) is centered around Liu, Malik, Stokes, and Tarba, who serve as full-time or visiting university professors in the United Kingdom. The fourth largest cluster (yellow, N=4) primarily comprises Dutch scholars Jansen, Tempelaar, and Volberda. Simsek, a member of this group, is a professor in the United States. The smallest cluster (purple, N=3) consists of Italian scholars Del Giudice, Ferraris, and Papa, affiliated with the universities of Rome and Turin, whose research interest connects organizational ambidexterity with innovation.

3.2.2 Co-(key)words/co-occurrence analysis

Co-(key)words, also known as a co-occurrence analysis, is a widely utilized science mapping technique that identifies and thematically links keywords within a collection of scholarly publications (Donthu et al., 2021). The resulting clusters consist of diverse yet related highlighted keywords, aiming to better illustrate the terminology and knowledge landscape across fields. Analyzing the frequency and impact of keywords organized into clusters of broader keywords makes it possible to identify specific authors, research groups, and emerging topics within the field to understand academic discourse (Lozano et al., 2019).

Figure 4: Co-authorship networks

Figure 5: Co-(key)words/co-occurrence networks

The study was based on author keywords as the primary unit of analysis to mitigate the potential influence of indexer bias in case essential components of the text have not been chosen accurately (Zupic & Cater, 2015). Out of 2,255 detected keywords, 89 met the threshold (the minimum number of occurrences of a keywords was five). The map finding showcased that all the topics concern the topic of ambidexterity (289 occurrences), and exploration (139 occurrences), exploitation (134 occurrences), organizational ambidexterity (118 occurrences), and innovation (74 occurrences) are the most widely used labels (see Figure 5). Organizational ambidexterity is linked to individual ambidexterity (16 occurrences) but does not correlate with any other level of ambidexterity; furthermore, no other levels of ambidexterity are represented in the map. The findings of this analysis consist of nine clusters (the minimum size was four) covering diverse yet complementary themes (see Table 4). Notably, multilevel ambidexterity research is forward-looking and addresses challenges encompassing intriguing and contemporary emerging topics. In this topic division, it is evident that scholars do not prioritize any specific level of ambidexterity as the primary focus; instead, they incorporate it within the context of their selected themes.

3.2.3 Co-citation analysis

Co-citation occurs when two or more secondary documents based on frequency are cited together by a third primary document, indicating a relationship between the cited works (Small, 1973). It identifies influential papers within a field by examining how frequently they are co-cited with other significant works, showcasing their impact on subsequent research (Garfield, 2006) or thematic categories (Zupic & Cater, 2015). It can identify interdisciplinary research areas, relevant literature, or research gaps.

Cited references were used as the unit of analysis, with a minimum threshold of 50, resulting in 103 publications (out of 38,893 cited documents) being included and classified into three thematic clusters (with a minimum cluster size of 20) (see Figure 6). The most substantial co-citation is March's (1991) influential paper "Exploration and Exploitation in Organizational Learning," published in *Organization Science* with 678 citations and a total link strength of 11,632.

Co-citation cluster 1 (red) is the largest and most influential cluster of publications (N=50), primarily comprising qualitative papers focused on

Table 4: Co-(key)words clusters

Cluster	Items	Themes	Main sub-themes
1	18	AMBIDEXTROUS INNOVATION & TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP	ambidextrous innovation, ambidextrous leadership, business model, business model innovation, dynamic capability, exploitative innovation, exploratory innovation, innovation strategy, intellectual capital, new product performance, transformational leaders, top management teams
2	15	EXPLORATION VS. EXPLOITATION TENSION	ambidexterity, culture, organizational design, organizational structure, paradox, projects, strategy, tension, uncertainty, cognition, disruptive innovation, emerging markets, entrepreneurship
3	14	SUSTAINABLE INNOVATION PRACTICES & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	corporate social responsibility, corporate sustainability, digital transformation, digitalization, dynamic capabilities, innovation performance, SME, sustainability, open innovation, family firm
4	11	AMBIDEXTROUS ORGANIZATIONAL LEADERSHIP	contextual ambidexterity, strategic ambidexterity, leadership, top management teams, organizational context, integration, corporate entrepreneurs, product innovation
5	9	AMBIDEXTROUS ORGANIZATION	ambidextrous learning, companies, organization, task analysis, organizational performance
6	7	EXPLORATION INTERNAL FACTORS	alliances, entrepreneurial orientation, learning, new ventures, market orientation, radical innovation
7	6	EXPLORATION EXTERNAL FACTORS	emerging economies, environmental uncertainty, innovation, strategic flexibility, knowledge management
8	5	ORGANIZATIONAL DESIGN & INDIVIDUAL OPTIMIZATION	business process management, human capital, organization design, organizational learning
9	4	AMBIDEXTERITY	exploration, exploitation, meta-analysis, performance

Figure 6: Co-citation clusters

navigating organizational ambidexterity to enhance performance, ambidextrous leadership, and multi-level frameworks exploring the relationship between organizational ambidexterity and interorganizational, team, and individual levels. Notably, 50% of the documents in this cluster were published in just five journals: *Organization Science* (7), *Journal of Management Studies* (6), *Academy of Management Journal* (4), *Academy of Management Review* (4), and *The Leadership Quarterly* (4). Additionally, 66% of the papers are co-authored by two (38%) or three (28%) authors, while 18% (N=9) are single-authored. A leading representative in the red cluster is the highly cited work by Gibson and Birkinshaw (2004), entitled “The Antecedents, Consequences, and Mediating Role of Organizational Ambidexterity,” published in the *Academy of Management Journal* (591 citations).

Co-citation cluster 2 (green) comprises 33 documents and is focused primarily on managing exploration and exploitation and their impact on performance through knowledge and process management. Compared to other clusters, almost 67% of the publications are concentrated in three top-tier scientific journals: *Strategic Management Journal* (11 or 22%), *Organization Science* (7), and *Academy of Management Review* (4). Like cluster 1, 18.18% of the publications are solo-authored, while over half (N=17) were written in pairs. The most influential paper in this cluster is Levinthal and March’s (1993) “The Myopia of Learning,” published in *Strategic Management Journal*.

Co-citation cluster 3 (blue), the smallest cluster (N=20), consists predominantly of documents focused on empirical studies, multivariate methods in social and psychological research, moderation and mediation models of exploration and exploitation, and team-level behavior. Scholars in this cluster primarily published in co-authorship teams of two, three, or four individuals (N=17 or 85%). Aside from two books, the publications appeared in various journals, with *Organization Science* (4) and *Journal of Management* (3) standing out. Alongside March’s most influential work, the second most cited paper in this cluster is Raisch and Birkinshaw’s (2008) “Organizational Ambidexterity: Antecedents, Outcomes, and Moderators,” published in the *Journal of Management*.

3.2.4 Bibliographic coupling

Bibliographic coupling occurs when two documents cite the same third document, indicating their relevance and a relationship based on shared ideas or findings through these common references (Kessler, 1963; Reyes-Gonzales et al., 2016). It resembles co-citation analysis, which refers to the present, but it is focused on frequently published recent primary papers that reference the same secondary sources emphasizing the future (Vogel et al., 2021). By effectively clustering recent publications, the analysis detects emerging thematic or niche areas of interest within a discipline and tracks the evolution of research trends, showcasing potential future directions.

The bibliographic coupling method was used to analyze 210 papers published between January 2022 and September 2024 without establishing a minimum citation threshold. The analysis revealed five equally distributed clusters with a minimum cluster size of 27 (see *Figure 7*). Among these publications, only 4.7% were single-authored. Most authors engaged in collaborative writing, with publications co-authored by groups of two (17.1%), three (34.76%), or four individuals (28.57%). The majority of papers were published in journals oriented to innovation and technology in the context of business and management: *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management* (11 documents), *Industrial Marketing Management* (8 documents), *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* (7 documents), *International Business Review* (6 documents), and *European Journal of Innovation Management* (6 documents).

The document with the highest coupling strength is by Audretsch and Guerrero (2023), published in the *Journal of Technology Transfer*. The authors explored organizational ambidexterity, emphasizing its dual tasks and the research gap in technology- and entrepreneurship-oriented journals regarding ambidexterity tensions. They presented five studies examining the interplay between entrepreneurship, innovation, and management across various global organizations.

Within the first cluster (N=51, red), the paper with the highest strength is by Ju and Elliott (2024), published in the *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*. They investigated the antecedents of or-

Figure 7: Bibliographic coupling clusters

organizational ambidexterity in foreign ventures within emerging markets, focusing on firm- and industry-level factors that influence the simultaneous pursuit of exploration and exploitation as an innovation strategy. Also within this cluster, Mendes et al. (2023), in their paper published in the *Journal of Technology Transfer*, examined how ambidextrous companies in industrial clusters balance exploration and exploitation to enhance innovation and innovation performance. Papers in the red cluster cover innovation, knowledge management, international ambidexterity, innovation ambidexterity, and technological learning and strategies.

In the second same-sized cluster (N=51, green), the standout publication is by Ambilichu et al. (2023) and published in the *European Management Review*. They investigated how strategic leadership influences the performance of UK accountancy firms, with findings showing that ambidexterity partially mediates this relationship. Additionally, El Manzani et al. (2023), in a paper published in the *European Journal of Innovation Management*, empirically analyzed the direct impacts of soft quality management practices and market orientation ambidexterity on product innovation ambidexterity. Papers in the green cluster explore themes such as

knowledge management, HRM, the link between organizational ambidexterity and performance, and the mediating and moderating factors influencing these relationships.

In addition to the aforementioned paper by Ju and Elliott (2024), the third cluster (N=50, blue) features a study by Escorcia-Caballero et al. (2024), published in *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, in which the authors examined the relationships among exploitation, exploration, and ambidexterity in organic agro-food processing companies to assess their impact on market performance while providing managerial guidance for enhancing ambidexterity. The cluster encompasses themes related to entrepreneurship, innovation, business models, and various forms of ambidexterity, including structural, sequential, and contextual ambidexterity.

In the fourth cluster (N=31, yellow), the paper with the highest strength is by Boemelburg et al. (2023), published in *Human Resource Management*. The study represents a multilevel model illustrating how the interplay between formal and informal organizational contexts fosters employee ambidexterity and behavior. In addition to focusing on

employee and individual ambidexterity and multi-level approaches, the cluster also covers topics such as moderation-mediation models and team ambidexterity.

The smallest cluster (N=27, purple) is focused on family-owned firms, SMEs, top management, leadership, and ventures. In the paper with the highest strength, by Hu et al. (2023) in the *Journal of Business Research*, the researchers examined the influence of organizational ambidexterity on firm performance, using family management and formalization as boundary conditions. Additionally, Van Doorn et al. (2022), in a paper published in *Long Range Planning*, explored how having a family CEO and top management team's family affiliations impact ambidexterity.

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This paper provides a comprehensive bibliometric review, integrating performance analysis and science mapping to deliver an objective, data-driven overview of multilevel ambidexterity literature. Following five key recommendations from Mukherjee et al. (2022), it is intended to “uncover knowledge clusters, map nomological networks depicting the field's current state, explore social patterns driving knowledge development, examine the field's evolutionary nuances, and identify knowledge gaps.” Based on the sensemaking approach (Lim & Kumar, 2024), the paper represents an attempt to accurately present the field's performance and intellectual structure to present past and present situations and inform future research. In its final phase, the paper adheres to credibility (rigorous methods), confirmability (objective findings and transparent search strategy and analytical process), and dependability (reproducibility checks) standards to substantiate its findings.

To enhance existing studies on ambidexterity, the bibliometric analysis was conducted using the WoSCC database, which includes a broad range of influential papers. Six unabbreviated keywords (covering core ambidexterity terms related to levels and their widely used synonyms) were applied for a more comprehensive yet precise search of multi-level ambidexterity research. Although this paper

is the first to focus on the multilevel nature of ambidexterity, its analysis is strategically framed within a 20-year context in management and business domains to enhance specific and in-depth understanding using the SSCI, which exclusively covers social sciences.

Performance analysis revealed that multilevel ambidexterity has evolved from a niche research topic into a more mainstream one, examining ambidexterity across various levels. Over time, scholars have introduced new levels, expanding the concept beyond its original scope. The multilevel ambidexterity field is widely published in leading scholarly journals, with four prominent co-authorship networks polarized between Western countries (e.g., the United States and the United Kingdom) and Eastern countries (e.g., China). Publication and citation trends are closely aligned, with authors who publish more frequently gaining more citations over time. Notably, many leading scholars in multilevel ambidexterity are also prominent in the field of organizational paradoxes, in which they maintain similar rankings. Older publications dominate citation trends, as more highly cited documents experience proportional citation growth over time.

Science mapping techniques identified knowledge clusters and intellectual structures for present and future research, indicating evolution (Chakma et al., 2024). Co-authorship analysis revealed the presence of closed groupings in which authors cluster based on factors such as country of origin or institutional affiliation. Highly cited leaders often collaborate with peers of similar status, producing further highly cited papers. Co-(key)word or co-occurrence analysis highlighted that new research topics predominantly revolve around ambidexterity, particularly organizational ambidexterity and its polarities. While organizational ambidexterity is linked to individual ambidexterity, no other levels are visibly connected. Nine contemporary topic clusters were identified, primarily focused on organizational ambidexterity, with other levels notably absent. Additionally, co-citation analysis revealed three seminal thematic clusters: (1) navigating organizational ambidexterity to improve performance, ambidextrous leadership, and multilevel frameworks examining the

relationships between organizational ambidexterity and interorganizational, team, and individual levels; (2) managing exploration and exploitation and their impact on performance via knowledge and process management; and (3) empirical studies, multivariate methods in social and psychological research, and team-level behavior, including moderation and mediation models of exploration and exploitation.

Furthermore, bibliographic coupling identified five promising research streams that have emerged in the past three years. These streams are focused on topics such as organizational ambidexterity in relation to theory or other fields (e.g., innovation and entrepreneurship), mediating–moderating research models, the evolution of organizational ambidexterity into interorganizational ambidexterity within emerging industries or markets, deeper exploration of team ambidexterity, and an increased focus on structural, sequential, and contextual forms of ambidexterity. Collaborative writing trends are expected to continue, with future publications likely to be more concentrated in journals focused on innovation and technology.

To sum up the analyses, the literature on multilevel ambidexterity is an emerging but still underexplored area in paradox research; some levels of ambidexterity are well-established and mature, while others are in the early stages of development (Nosella et al., 2012). Organizational ambidexterity will continue to serve as a benchmark in future research as a critical bridge between interorganizational, team (unit), or individual (employee) ambidexterity and performance. A review of research outputs shows that multilevel ambidexterity is not a distinct research field but is positioned as a psychological or strategic phenomenon intersecting other areas. As such, multilevel ambidexterity represents a crossroads of management, business, and broader domains, making it particularly challenging for qualitative analysis. This raises questions about its utility—if the concept becomes overly flexible, it risks losing analytical clarity and power (Popadić & Milohnić, 2016). The study highlights the repetition of the same authors and papers, indicating the difficulty of surpassing the dominance of existing leaders in this rapidly growing field.

Echoing the observations made by Popadić and Milohnić (2016), this paper reveals the prevailing ambiguity within the field, highlighted by many studies. Most papers utilize one or a few levels of ambidexterity. However, authors typically approach these concepts in a conceptual rather than an empirical (multivariate) manner, not as the keyword selection suggests. Unfortunately, the analysis does not clarify whether the findings on multilevel ambidexterity arise from organizations' actual needs or merely reflect current academic trends. Additionally, the study is susceptible to established literature patterns emphasizing well-known citations, making it unclear whether these citations are based on intrinsic quality (Garcia-Lillo et al., 2017). The analysis also fails to include papers that may have been published recently, given that the WoS platform requires time to update its listings. As a solo-authored paper, the potential for subjective bias in the qualitative interpretation of findings cannot be eliminated (Lim & Kumar, 2024). While there is no definitive bibliographic search method that can yield the best results for comprehensive research areas such as multilevel ambidexterity, the results can be influenced by keyword selection, filtering criteria, and the exclusive reliance on a single database, which may not capture the complete spectrum of relevant literature.

The paper offers practical contributions by adhering to Mukherjee et al.'s (2022) five key recommendations, which include “enabling an objective assessment and reporting of research productivity and impact, examining the coverage or reach of research, identifying social dominance or hidden biases, highlighting anomalies for further exploration, and evaluating relative performance for equitable decision-making.” In addition to encouraging scholars to advance the development of the field across all levels of ambidexterity, the paper also offers guidance for managers and practitioners on how to integrate diverse ambidextrous strategies at various organizational levels effectively. Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of identifying various multilevel ambidexterity practices or processes and aligning them with existing policies to navigate or mitigate ambidextrous polarities within their organizations for better performance.

5 FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The concept of ambidexterity within organizations remains inconclusive or consistently redefined within the research community. However, future studies are expected to refine its conceptualization by increasingly framing ambidexterity as a paradoxical construct, offering more profound insights into its multidimensional nature and implications within organizations. Given that ambidexterity naturally cascades across organizational levels and operates dynamically within real-world contexts, its multi-level nature can no longer be overlooked or bypassed by researchers from a conceptual or empirical (multivariate) perspective. Researchers should place greater emphasis on advancing the concept of external ambidexterity. In contrast, within the realm of internal ambidexterity, increased attention should be directed toward secondary (team/unit ambidexterity) and tertiary (individual/employee ambidexterity) levels (Nosella et al., 2012). Furthermore, future studies should be designed to theoretically delineate the distinctions between team- or unit-level ambidexterity and individual- or employee-level ambidexterity. One certainty is that organizational ambidexterity will remain a foundational reference point, acting as a critical link that connects interorganizational, team (unit), and individual (employee) ambidexterity with performance outcomes, whether examined from a bottom-up or top-down perspective or through mediating or moderating factors. Within this context, the dualities of organizational ambidexterity—exploration and exploitation—will persist as a *sine qua non*, essential for understanding its role and interplay in achieving sustained performance and adaptability, whether through multiplicative or additive integration. This yet-to-be-uncovered but anticipated knowledge is expected to be pivotal in enabling managers and practitioners to effectively navigate and integrate diverse ambidextrous strategies across multiple organizational levels. Given theoretical directions on ambidexterity, they are expected to be closely integrated with the contexts of innovation, entrepreneurship, and knowledge management, fostering collaborative writing with an increased tendency toward publication in innovation- and technology-focused journals.

To address empirical limitations, future studies could enhance the interpretation of findings through collaboration with other researchers for a more objective and comprehensive perspective. While the existing methodology is adequate, it could be expanded to include advanced analyses such as content analysis, sentimental analysis, factor analysis, or social network analysis, as suggested by Chakma et al. (2024). Additionally, incorporating publications from the Scopus database alongside the updated WoSCC used in this research could enrich future studies on multi-level ambidexterity. Adopting a more dynamic approach (Zahoor et al., 2021) through longitudinal studies could provide insights into how multilevel ambidexterity evolves in practice (Turner et al., 2012). Future researchers might also consider conducting bibliometric analyses on each ambidexterity level (e.g., team or individual) to expand the scope to examine ambidexterity dimensions (internal vs. external) separately (Gibson & Birkinshaw, 2004) in conjunction with comparative studies among these levels or dimensions. Moreover, focusing on specific or emerging industries or sectors (Chakma et al., 2024) could foster interdisciplinary insights or uncover unique manifestations of ambidexterity within diverse organizational contexts. In the substantiating phase, demonstrating the relevance of findings across various subfields (Lim & Kumar, 2024) could enhance transferability, and employing temporal analyses and methodological triangulation would enhance the dependability of research outcomes (Donthu et al., 2022). Ultimately, replicating this study in the future could yield valuable insights into the field's evolution (Snehvrat et al., 2017).

EXTENDED SUMMARY/IZVLEČEK

Večnivojska ambidekstrija je nastajajoča, a še vedno premalo raziskana tema v okviru proučevanja organizacijskih paradoksov. Čeprav je organizacijska ambidekstrija že dobro uveljavljena in konceptualno izoblikovana raven analize, raziskave o ambidekstriji na ravni enot oziroma timov ter na ravni delovnih mest oziroma posameznikov ostajajo v zgodnji fazi razvoja. Z namenom priprave posodobljenega in integrativnega pregleda literature o trenutni strukturi, raziskovalnih trendih in vrzelih na področju ambidekstrije je bila izvedena bibliometrična analiza. Cilj je bil ovrednotiti pretekli razvoj (analiza uspešnosti), preučiti sedanost (analiza soavtorstva, sopojavljanja ključnih besed in so-citiranja) ter predvideti prihodnje usmeritve raziskovanja (analiza bibliografske povezanosti) na ravneh medorganizacijske, organizacijske, enotne (timske) in individualne (zaposleni oziroma delovno mesto) ambidekstrije. Iskanje je bilo opravljeno v podatkovni zbirki Web of Science Core Collection, pri čemer je bilo zajetih 900 primarnih in 24.742 sekundarnih predhodno filtriranih znanstvenih objav, ki pokrivajo obdobje do septembra 2024. Ugotovitve mapiranja znanstvenega področja usmerjajo raziskovalce k oblikovanju prihodnjih teoretičnih in strateških okvirov, ki bodo organizacijskim praktikom pomagali pri obvladovanju izzivov uravnoteženja na različnih ravneh analize.

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